

of the test solution was 100 to 150 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and the inocula for the purpose were 24 hr old and were prepared from stationary culture and the results were standardised against benzoic acid. No encouraging results were obtained.

Experimental

The aryl styryl ketones recorded in Table I have been prepared by adopting the method of Misra⁹ *et al.* One typical example is cited below.

Saturated solution of sodium in methanol (5–10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring to an aldehyde free alcoholic solution of 2-acetyl naphthalene and 2-bromo benzaldehyde (0.005 mol). After 24 hr the dark coloured reaction mixture was kept in refrigerator and separated yellow coloured plates were purified by recrystallisation from alcohol. Finally the purity was checked by TLC as reported earlier¹¹.

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References

1. E. SCHRAUFSTATTER and S. DEUTSCH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1948, 3b, 163.
2. S. S. MISRA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, 40(A), 468.
3. S. C. KUSHWAHA and S. S. MISRA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, 40(A), 301.
4. S. S. MISRA, *Labdev J. Sci. & Tech. (India)*, 1971, 8(A), 152.
5. E. SCHRAUFSTATTER and S. DEUTSCH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1948, 3b, 430.
6. Y. TAKAYANAGI, *Ann. Rept. Teheku Coll. Pharm.*, 1954, No. 1, 10; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, 50, 4989e.
7. S. S. MISRA, and J. B. LAL, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. (India)*, 1970, 40(A), 296.
8. J. K. EATON and R. G. DAVIES, *Ann. Rept. Appl. Bio.*, 1950, 37, 471.
9. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 260.
10. S. S. MISRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 69.
11. D. N. DHAR and S. S. MISRA, *J. Chromatog.*, 1972, 69, 416.
12. C. W. WILSON and D. E. FLEYPD, *J. Pharm. Exptl. Therap.*, 1949, 95, 399.
13. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 637.
14. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, 35, 95.
15. S. S. MISRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 209.
16. S. S. MISRA, *Monat. fur Chemie*, 1973, 11, 105.
17. W. B. GEIGER and J. E. CONN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 112.
18. K. K. HSU and F. C. CHEN, *Tai-Wan K' Hsueh*, 1973, 27, 236.
19. S. S. MISRA and R. S. TEWARI, *Labdev. J. Sci. & Tech.*, 1971, 9A, 222.
20. S. S. MISRA and S. C. KUSHWAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
21. D. N. DHAR and S. S. MISRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 629.
22. S. S. MISRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 909.
23. P. F. DEVITT, A. TIMONEY and M. A. VICKARS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 4941.
24. D. N. DHAR and J. B. LAL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1159.
25. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press).
26. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 639.
27. M. KAMODA, *J. Agr. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1954, 28, 791.
28. S. S. MISRA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 211.
29. R. KUHN and H. R. HENSEL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1953, 86, 1333.

Potentiometric Study of Copper(II) Complexes of L-Hydroxyproline

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AMINO acids which form stable complexes have analytical importance in separation of transition metals, and rare earths¹. A study of these complexes is also important in biological chemistry, in that the accumulation of sufficient data on amino acid complexes with metal ions may contribute to a better understanding of the types of linkages involved in metal-protein interactions. There are scanty references²⁻⁵ on the chelate forming tendency of hydroxyproline. In the present communication, the formation of copper(II) chelate with hydroxyproline was studied using Bjerrum's and Calvin's method as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶. The stepwise stability constants of the metal chelate were determined by Rossotti and Rossotti procedure.

Experimental

Materials. Copper nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) was used without further purification. 0.01M stock solution of the copper nitrate was standardised by titration with EDTA (AnalaR, disodium salt) using PAN indicator⁷. L-hydroxyproline (E. Merck), sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and nitric acid (AnalaR) were used. pH measurements were done by ELICO p-Meter model LI-12, using a glass-calomel electrode assembly at 30°. The pH-meter was standardised with buffer solution prepared from buffer tablets (B.D.H.) for pH 4.0 and pH 9.2 at 30°. All solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

Titration Procedure. Mixture containing (a) acid (10 ml of 0.5M potassium nitrate and 5 ml of 0.01M nitric acid), (b) ligand (mixture (a) and 10 ml of 0.025M hydroxyproline), (c) complex (mixture (b) and 5 ml of 0.01M Cu(NO₃)₂ solution) was taken, and total volume made upto 50 ml. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 by KNO₃ solution. Mixture a, b and c were separately titrated with a standard carbonate free 0.2N KOH solution delivered from micro burette.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves using solutions (a) and (b) the number of hydrogen ions bound to the ligand anion ($\bar{n}_H$) was calculated and plotted against pH to obtain the formation curve for proton ligand system. The pK_a value corresponding to $\bar{n}_H = 1/2$ was obtained from the curve as 9.35. However, the best

using the value of K_1 and K_2 . The satisfactory agreement between $\bar{n}_{cal.}$ and $\bar{n}_{expt.}$ were obtained but the deviation between them were more in higher alkaline medium and which might be due to the deprotonation of $>NH$ group. The overall free energy (ΔF) = $-RT \ln \beta_2$ was calculated as -21.95 Kcal/mole.

Fig(1) Plot of $\text{Log} \left(\frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H} \right)$ vs pH .

Fig(3) Computation of β_1 and β_2 from the plot of Rossotti and Rossotti functions.

value of pK_a of the ligand was found from the plot of $\log (\bar{n}_H/(1-\bar{n}_H))$ vs. pH . This plot (fig. 1) was found to be straight line with intercept equal to pK_a and slope equal to unity suggesting that only one proton was dissociated. The pK_a value thus obtained was 9.34, showed good agreement as reported by other workers^{2,8}.

From the titration curves using solutions (a), (b) and (c), $\bar{n}$ values of the metal complex were determined at various pH values. From these data, the corresponding PL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values then plotted against the corresponding PL values to get the formation curve of the metal complex equilibria (Fig. 2). The formation curve of the metal-ligand system attained maxima at $\bar{n} > 1.5$ indicating that 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were formed. From the analysis of the formation curve it was clear that the ratio of stepwise stability constant (K_1/K_2) was less than $10^{2.5}$, hence the method of interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values would give only the approximate values of the stability constants⁶ and better values might be computed using Rossotti and Rossotti method. The stability constant ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) obtained from Rossotti and Rossotti plot (Fig. 3) were found to be 8.34 and 7.39 respectively. This was further checked by constructing a theoretical formation curve from the values of PL and $\bar{n}$ and $\bar{n}$ was obtained from the equation

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})[L]} = K_1 + K_2 K_1 \frac{(2-\bar{n})[L]}{(1-\bar{n})}$$

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Fig (2) Formation curve of Cu (II) Complex of L-hydroxyproline

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References

1. S. LAL, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 1571.
2. J. SCHUBERT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3442.
3. N. C. LI, B. E. DODDY and J. M. WHITE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 5901.
4. D. D. FERRIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 290.
5. F. KARCZYNSKI and G. S. KUPRY, *Recs. Chem.*, 1970, 44(55), 967.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
7. C. N. REILLEY, R. W. SCHID and F. S. SADEK, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1959, 36, 555, 619.
8. P. L. KIRK and C. L. A. SCHMIDT, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 81, 237.

Synthesis of New Organotin Compounds for Protection of Crops

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MEHROTRA and Dey¹ reported earlier the preparation of new organotin compounds as potential pesticidal agents. We have extended²⁻⁴ this work to incorporate fatty acids of coconut oil

and aliphatic alcohols in organotin compounds and is reported in this communication. The general steps of the reaction are as follows :

Organotin compounds from

(i) *Aliphatic acids*

(1) ALIPHATIC ACIDS

(ii) ALIPHATIC ALCOHOLS

TABLE I—PROPERTIES OF SYNTHESISED ORGANOMERCURY AND TIN COMPOUNDS

Sl. No.	Nature of R and R'	Mercury compounds		Tin compounds		Pesticidal properties of tin compounds					
		M.P. °C and yeild	Mercury percentage Found Calculated	M.P. °C yeild/ and colour	Tin percentage Found Theoretical	A.N.	C.G.	R.S.	E.C.	S.A.	
d Aliphatic acid where R											
1.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆	206, 52	41.4 41.8	185(d), 45, Y	31.3 31.6	++	++	++	++	+	
2.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₈	200, 58	39.1 39.5	170(d), 46, F	29.2 29.4	+	+	+	++	+	
3.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₀	213, 60	37.3 37.4	168(d), 48, W	27.2 27.5	+	+	+	+	+	
4.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂	225, 61	35.0 35.5	152, 50, W	25.4 25.8	+	+	+	+	+	
5.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₄	210, 65	33.4 33.9	177, 52, Y	24.3 24.3	+	-	+	-	-	
6.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₆	180, 65	32.0 32.3	205, 48, W.Y	22.6 23.0	+	+	+	-	+	
7.	CH ₃	210, 56	50.2 50.7	180(d), 46, Y	40.6 40.9	+	+	+	+	-	
8.	CH ₃ CH ₂	193, 60	48.6 49.0	170(d), 50, WG	38.6 39.0	+	+	-	-	+	
9.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂	165, 54	47.0 47.3	232, 48, W.Y	37.0 37.2	+	+	+	-	-	
Aliphatic alcohols where R'											
1.	C ₃ H ₇	165, 58	50.4 50.7	152, 44, W	38.6 40.9	+	+	+	-	-	
2.	C ₄ H ₉	150, 60	48.8 49.0	185, 42, D.Y	38.5 39.0	++	++	++	-	+	
3.	C ₅ H ₁₁	195, 55	47.0 47.3	171, 41, D.G	37.0 37.2	+	+	+	-	+	
4.	C ₆ H ₁₃	186, 59	45.2 45.8	160, 43, F	35.2 35.7	++	-	-	+	-	
5.	C ₇ H ₁₅	210, 60	44.2 44.4	164, 46, G	34.0 34.2	++	++	+	++	+	
6.	C ₁₂ H ₂₅	205, 54	38.1 38.4	176, 48, Y	28.4 28.7	++	++	+	++	+	
7.	C ₁₆ H ₃₃	196, 55	34.5 34.7	156, 43, Y	24.7 25.0	+	+	+	+	+	

+ Stand for 0-50 /increased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 ++ Stand for 51-100/increased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 - Stand for 51-100/decreased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 Y—Yellow, F—Fawn, W—White, Y—Yellow, WY—Whitish yellow, WG—Whitish grey, DY—Dark yellow, D.G.—Dark grey, d—decomposed.

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